

WP4 (Taiwan) Civil Society Engagement Report

Second Workshop on HRJust Civil Society Engagement and Discussion

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Civil Society Engagement Report: Second Workshop on HRJust Civil Society Engagement and Discussion, 22 March 2025

As part of our Civil Society Engagement, the WP4 Taiwan team held a series of events including two workshops, with the intention of generating ideas and key points in the first and then bringing back participants from the first round to share our preliminary research findings. The second workshop “HRJust: Civil Society Engagement and Discussion”, took place on 22 March 2025 with invited experts in civic tech, labor rights, law, and medical history as discussants.

From Borders to Bodies: A Population-Centered Approach in Taiwan’s Pandemic Response

Countries responded to COVID-19 differently, even after scientists and epidemiologists had developed a common understanding of the coronavirus and its method of transmission.¹ A Taiwanese scholar of medical history noted that this divergence could be explained by “path dependency,” whereby each country adopted accustomed tactics and relied on its existing resources to address the epidemic. In Taiwan, factors such as geography, history, economic dependence on trade, its legal infrastructure, plus the barrier of vaccine access due to China’s obstruction, jointly led to population-centered interventions such as border closure, quarantine, isolation, and massive digital measures.

Taiwan, as an island nation, is accustomed to leveraging its geographic isolation to prevent the entry and spread of infectious diseases.² Upon learning about the coronavirus discovered in Wuhan, China, the Taiwanese government promptly closed borders and enforced quarantine and isolation, mainly targeting “higher risk” nations and populations.

Our previous Civil Society Engagement (CSE) report pointed out that it was common in Taiwan that the government deployed the police to conduct contact tracing and to enforce quarantine during the pandemic (see Focus Group

¹PETER BALDWIN, *FIGHTING THE FIRST WAVE: WHY THE CORONAVIRUS WAS TACKLED SO DIFFERENTLY ACROSS THE GLOBE* (2021).

²For example, in order to prevent the spread of AIDS, Taiwan required foreigners to present a negative HIV test result upon entry until the provision was abolished in 2015. (According to the repealed Article 14 of the AIDS Prevention and Control Act, foreigners entering or residing in Taiwan for more than three months must receive a HIV test or submit a HIV test result within three months. Foreigners who test positive must be deported.

Interview with People Who Underwent Quarantine, p. 1-3). The engagement of the police force may not have triggered wide public concerns as, historically, similar practices existed during the time Taiwan was under the rule of Imperial China (Qing dynasty) and Japan.³ Nevertheless, our Focus Group participants strongly criticized these path-dependent practices, which caused various problems. For example, the police intervened in contact tracing with crime investigation mentality and techniques, disrupting the trust-based relationship that public health professionals aim to develop with the subject. For the public, having multiple agencies taking part in the process without clearly identifying themselves or their source of authority makes it difficult for individuals to challenge dispositive actions and seek legal remedies.

Where and How Can We Access Source Code? – Barriers to Transparency

In addition to historical and geographic factors, the historian of medicine considered that Taiwan's ability to deploy targeted and meticulous digital measures can also be attributed to robust administrative capacity and infrastructure, including the establishment of the National Health Insurance (NHI) database and its linkage with other public and private data. Since the NHI launched as a mandatory insurance in 1995, its database has collected massive amounts of personal health data.

An active participant in the civic tech community, the g0v (gov-zero) – one of the recruitment targets of our surveys – further expressed his concerns about the transparency of such measures. The source code of many pandemic control digital tools was unavailable, e.g., digital fencing (used for enforcing quarantine) and 1922 SMS (used for contact tracing). This hindered civil society from auditing the systems, a process that could enhance information security and uncover hidden risks of privacy intrusion. The g0v contributor suggested that the government establish a centralized repository for source code. Adopting such a system also needs consideration of which authority is accountable for managing the repository.

A Working Condition Comparison between Pilots and Glove Factory Workers

When digital tools were deployed to enforce quarantine, pilots were disproportionately affected due to their frequent cross-border travel. As noted in

³Shi-yung Lui, *An Overview of Public Health Development in Japan-ruled Taiwan*, in *DEATH AT THE OPPOSITE ENDS OF THE EURASIAN CONTINENT—MORTALITY TRENDS IN TAIWAN AND THE NETHERLANDS 1850-1945* 165, 170 (Theo Engelen, John R. Shepherd, & Yang Wen-shan eds., 2011).

our previous CSE report on the focus group with pilots, they were stuck in relentless cycles of flying and quarantine (see Focus Group Interview with Pilots, Section: Deteriorating Working Conditions). A labor rights advocate compared their treatment during the pandemic to that of workers working in a disposable glove company in Malaysia. The profit of airlines with cargo services surged as demand for air freight increased during the pandemic. Similarly, the glove company's profits skyrocketed as the demand for PPE persisted. The latter was accused of forced labor (most of the staff were migrant workers), triggering international condemnation.⁴ Although pilots are typically considered a high-income group, prolonged quarantine that severely restricts freedom of movement may be regarded as inhumane or exploitative treatment. The absence of additional compensation for severe freedom restrictions and the burdens on mental health also raised concerns that their working conditions may meet some of the indicators of forced labor.

Shifting Stance of Judicial Review: Late-Stage Oversight of Pandemic Measures

As discussed, population-centered measures targeted “higher risk” individuals, yet their efficacy was unknown because researchers were unable to access relevant data. Despite such difficulties, a judge of the Taipei High Administrative Court reported that in the later stages of the pandemic, the courts, as a major oversight mechanism, have challenged some mandates and sided with the plaintiffs (affected individuals). For instance, in several cases the Court held that the Central Epidemic Command Center (CECC) announcing mandates in the daily press conferences failed to meet due process requirements and were therefore in violation of the law.⁵ In another ruling, the Supreme Administrative Court held that the CECC’s setting a priority list for vaccines and associating fines for violators in the “COVID-19 vaccination program” (“the Program”) did not meet the necessary procedural requirements. The Court ruled that the program is an “order” as defined under the Administrative Procedure Act and must be issued via the Official Gazette. As the Program had been declared solely through CECC’s press conference, the Court found it to be invalid.⁶

A law professor further argued that the CECC functioned only as a coordinating organ, and held no power to impose mandates. Epidemic measures must be issued and enforced by the competent authorities, i.e., the relevant

⁴Julie Zaugg, *The world's top suppliers of disposable gloves are thriving because of the pandemic. Their workers aren't*, CNN (Sep. 11, 2020), <https://edition.cnn.com/2020/09/11/business/malaysia-top-glove-forced-labor-dst-intl-hnk> (last visited Jan. 26, 2026)

⁵Taipei High Administrative Court Ruling 110-Su-1153 [臺北高等行政法院110年度訴字第1153號判決], Taipei High Administrative Court Ruling 111-Su-113 [臺北高等行政法院111年度訴字第113號判決]

⁶Supreme Administrative Court Ruling 112-Shang-630 [最高行政法院112年度上字第630號]

ministries and local governments. This opinion directly responds to the concern raised by the attorney of the Air Line Pilots Association (ALPA-T), who noted that the CECC bypassed the competent authorities and directly imposed quarantine on pilots. According to this view, the CECC had no competence to restrict personal freedom because its role is restricted to coordination and therefore that the quarantine mandate would be invalid.

Substantive Review: Application of the Principle of Proportionality

In addition to procedural issues, the court also used substantive reasoning to invalidate several pandemic measures. The Administrative Court judge noted that quarantine measures that failed to consider special needs or that involved arbitrary assignments to quarantine locations were often found to violate the principle of proportionality.⁷ The law professor further emphasized that, in response to the rising frequency of crises, the amendments to the Communicable Disease Control Act should address various needs for quarantine arrangements while also preventing potential human rights violations arising from such measures.

Some Problems are Tackled, Others Are Not – What is the Next Step?

That the later-stage rulings tend to be in favor of plaintiffs reiterates what our participants in the first round of CSE said: “it was not easy to challenge pandemic measures promptly due to the unpredictable nature of the crisis. Nevertheless, a comprehensive assessment of proportionality remains vital once the emergency has subsided (see First Workshop: COVID-19 Governance in Taiwan, p. 2).”

We found that some of the issues raised in the first round of discussions (Workshop 1) have been alleviated as the oversight mechanism has resumed functioning. For instance, quarantine measures that failed to provide accommodation for individuals with special needs (such as injured persons, pregnant women and minors) as well as arbitrary quarantine arrangements, would not pass the proportionality test (see Focus Group Interview with Frontline Health Professionals, Section: Pandemic Measures Lacking Accommodations for Special Needs & Focus Group Interview with People Who Underwent Quarantine, Section: Pandemic Measures Fail to Address Needs of Minors and Parents). Mandates that did not meet the procedural requirements were declared invalid by the courts.

However, some concerns rooted in institutional design remain unresolved

⁷Supreme Administrative Court Ruling 111-Shang-642 [最高行政法院111年度上字第642號判決]

and warrant legislative reform.

- Suggestion 1: Open Data for Pandemic Assessment

Since access to pandemic-related data is often limited, civil society faces significant challenges in evaluating both the efficacy and necessity of the digital measures, as well as the extent of privacy intrusions of these measures. So far, the government has disclosed only limited data regarding two contact tracing tools – the SMS check-in and the Social Distancing APP (local version of the Google-Apple Bluetooth-based contact tracing). As a result, even though police surveillance and roadside searches were widely regarded as excessive, civil society found it difficult to hold the government accountable.

“[Indicator Framework to Evaluate the Public Health Effectiveness of Digital Proximity Tracing Solutions](#),” published by the WHO and the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, proposed five methods of data collection for assessing the effectiveness of a contact tracing app: (1) data obtained from the digital proximity tracing network, (2) integration with conventional contact tracing, (3) data collected at testing services, (4) surveys, and (5) data donation. To ensure government accountability in balancing public health with the protection of individuals’ freedom, with appropriate privacy safeguards in place, Taiwan should make certain data available. It is also important to note that during Taiwan’s extended zero-COVID period, when traditional contact tracing methods might have been sufficient, the effectiveness of digital measures in comparison with traditional methods should be measured carefully, e.g. based on the additional number of confirmed cases that could not be identified without digital measures.

- Suggestion 2: Correcting and Strengthening the Conditions for Secondary Use of Personal Data under Taiwan’s Personal Data Protection Act (PDPA)

The primary reason why Taiwan was able to introduce massive digital measures was due to the lack of an up-to-date personal data protection framework that could effectively keep the government’s digital surveillance in check. In 2022, the Taiwan Constitutional Court (TCC) issued Judgment 111-Hsien-Pan-13 (Case on the National Health Insurance Research Database) on the secondary use of NHI data without prior consent. TCC ruled that both the purposes for collecting and processing data in the NHI database, as well as the secondary use of such data, must be clearly prescribed by law. In reviewing the broader data protection regime, TCC further declared the Personal Data Protection Act (PDPA) in place at the time to be unconstitutional. It emphasized the need for the PDPA to establish an independent supervisory mechanism and to guarantee individuals’

right to opt out.⁸

This 2022 ruling accelerated one of the most significant amendments to the PDPA since its enactment in 1995. The revised PDPA, promulgated in 2025, established a unified competent authority for data protection – the Personal Data Protection Commission (PDPC). However, the PDPC remains in the preparatory stage, and the Regulations governing PDPC, which are essential to ensuring the Commission’s independence as required by the TCC, have not yet been passed.

Further, Congress also enacted the National Health Insurance Data Management Act in December 2025, introducing individuals’ right to opt out of secondary NHI data use. Nevertheless, this right is constrained, as the Act permits the government to conduct secondary use without consent in cases where it is doing so in order to perform its statutory duties.

In retrospect, Taiwan’s PDPA has fallen short of GDPR standards — more precisely, the Act’s broadly permissive framework governing the secondary use of sensitive personal data and inter-database linkage has created significant regulatory gaps. As a result, not only were large-scale digital surveillance measures readily authorized during the pandemic crisis, but Big Data and Artificial Intelligence applications involving sensitive personal data — particularly medical, health, and genetic information — have equally been able to obtain PDPA authorization with relative ease. In the absence of comprehensive legislative reform, it remains uncertain whether comparable privacy-intrusive measures of such scale would once again be sanctioned in the event of a future crisis.

- Suggestion 3: Issues rooted in institutional culture require more attention

Other issues stemmed from institutional cultures and historical practices that require further examination. “Escape into private law,” identified in the CSE report illustrates how pilots were placed in a dual predicament or double bind (see Focus Group Interview with Pilots, Section: Government by Proxy: Pressuring Airlines to Regulate Pilots). On the one hand, they did not have a standing to file a lawsuit against the government; on the other hand, they were rarely willing to challenge the airlines due to fear of losing their jobs. Therefore, it is vital to consider how to constrain government overreach in highly regulated industries, while ensuring that workers have sufficient resources and bargaining power to counterbalance those of their employers. Lastly, police involvement in public health enforcement, though historically rooted, should not be accepted as normal

⁸Taiwan Constitutional Court, *Summary of TCC Judgment 111-Hsien-Pan-13 (2022) Case on the National Health Insurance Research Database* (Aug. 12, 2022), <https://cons.judicial.gov.tw/en/docdata.aspx?fid=5535&id=347736> (last visited Jan. 26, 2026)

and reasonable.

To conclude our Civil Society Engagement, we recall a participant’s observation at our first workshop: that the government’s mindset that “the right to life trumps everything” was used by the government as an apparent justification for sacrificing all other human rights. The impacts of the government’s mindset on this point is repeatedly observed throughout the CSE process, and this calls for continued reflection, especially when facing future pandemics.